

Updatable Queue Protocol Based On TCP For Virtual Reality Environment

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ABSTRACT

The variance in number and types of tasks required to be implemented within Distributed Virtual Environments (DVE) highlights the needs for communication protocols can achieve consistency. In addition, these applications have to handle an increasing number of participants and deal with the difficult problem of scalability. Moreover, the real-time requirements of these applications make the scalability problem more difficult to solve. In this paper, we have implemented Updatable Queue Abstraction protocol (UQA) on TCP (TCP-UQA) and compared it with original TCP, UDP, and Updatable Queue Abstraction based on UDP (UDP-UQA) protocols. Results showed that TCP-UQA was the best in queue management.

KEYWORDS

updatable queue abstraction, distributed virtual reality, communication protocols.

1. INTRODUCTION

Virtual Environments (VE) applications usually consist of many different tasks that vary considerably from interfacing with input and output devices, through providing responsive user interaction, to simulating a dynamic environment. This variance in number and types of tasks required to be implemented within VE applications raised the idea of implementing VE applications over a distributed environments which in turn raised new tasks and issues to be considered such obtaining tracking and hand input information through continuous communication with external devices, rendering processes that require graphics intensive computation, and processes that perform collision detection between entities of the environment and simulate movement and behaviors for those entities. Distributed Virtual Environments (DVE) systems generally transmit a great deal of state update messages between tasks and require only the most recent state available. In addition, old state information is not only useless in most cases; it is harmful for the running tasks and for the systems as a whole. So how information is communicated between tasks is critical.

DVE systems communicate through two types of communication modes. First, one-to-one communication, which is happened within processes that interface external devices, usually done using a client-server connections using the TCP/IP protocol, For example, Rubber Rocks application and the MR toolkit [1], which describes a network software architecture for solving the problem of scaling very large distributed simulations. The fundamental idea is to logically

partition virtual environments by associating spatial, temporal, and functionally related entityclasses with network multicast group. The second is one-to-many communication, which happened among processes that share a common state.

Within DVE there are three types of messages: the status update message, the command message, and the event message. The status update message represents a stream of state descriptions. This description may be, for example, a three dimensional position of the node, periodically and fast changing in the stock exchange, and so on.

Figure 1: Messages types in DVE.

If the delivery of every state description message is guaranteed, then the receiving task will need to read all of the obsolete information before obtaining the latest state information (bandwidth cost), to decrease sending frequency one can implement a flow control, but this will increase the average lag time (delay between sending and receiving a message). On the other hand, if messages delivery is not guaranteed the same overflow problem occurs, but less frequently (whereas old messages will be automatically dropped if not received within a certain amount of time). [2]

The command message conveys instructions from one task to another. Unlike the status message, the command message does not become obsolete. When the node sends a command message it must guarantee delivery to the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) order, so it required an acknowledgement message from the receiver. Command messages used also to obtain state information from another task by this it uses fewer messages than state update communication, receives the most current information possible, but the client must block and wait for a response.[2]

Figure 2: command message.

The last message type is the event message which communicates the occurrence of events like key-presses; button presses, or object collisions. Unlike the command message, the event message does not require an acknowledgement message. Like the command message, the event message is unique in that, it does not become obsolete and could occur frequently. The event message must be guaranteed and FIFO delivery order. However, it needs state to work, so the last state update messages before the event cannot become obsolete until after the event has been processed. In this type of messages, the client does not need to block for a response when it is used to obtain state information from another task, but if the response arrived early, then the information will become old. One can solve it by timing the arriving of the message which is difficult to predict. [2]

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section two discusses the related works. Section three presents the implementation of the proposed model. The results are presented in section four. In section five, we present the conclusion and the future work.

2. RELATED WORKS

The most common transport layer protocols that are used in distributed virtual environment communications are the Transport Control Protocol (TCP), which guarantees reliable transmission across a distributed environment, and the User Datagram Protocol (UDP).

For short-term interactions, when the amount of information is small and it needs to be transmitted on an irregular basis, UDP is preferred over TCP. On the other hand, for long-term interactions, when data needs to be sent regularly or a large amount of data needs to be transmitted, then TCP is to be preferred. Another issue worth noting is that the UDP protocol does not guarantee message delivery to the receiving node. While the TCP, from the other hand, guarantees the message delivery, but congests the network with the acknowledgement messages. Thus there is a trade-off between the quantity of data to be transmitted and the regularity of transmission. SPLINE [3], overcomes the problem of the acknowledgements by sending messages with complete object state. Even if some messages are lost, consistency can be restored when the next message arrives.

Several protocols were used within distributed virtual environment trying to achieve consistency and message traffic issues. State message update was one of the critical issues for distributed virtual environment upon its importance and impact, where it is the only way that defines and keeps track the status of each component in the distributed virtual environment. Without having the

recent state, the tasks can't be accomplished at all or it will be not correct where resources spent on performing on obsolete information. TCP/IP was used within distributed virtual environment but it didn't suit all types of these applications where it didn't allow messages to be deliberately dropped. This forces any task wants the recent state of another task to hear all of its obsolete states which will be time and bandwidth costly. On the other hand, it was necessary to use TCP with applications require very high degree of objects state accuracies such as virtual medical environments. UDP allowed dropping messages which decreases the message traffic, but it didn't allow the application to decide which messages are dropped. Distributed Interactive Simulation (DIS) protocol which used by NPSNET [4], which is developed on a peer-to-peer network topology, uses UDP Broadcast or multicast communication. It simulate other peers through using the *dead reckoning* algorithm, which simulates state changes locally so a peer only broadcast its state when it has changed within a threshold error from what other processes will simulate, This protocol is not a general solution to communication between distributed virtual environment tasks because event and command communication require ordered and guaranteed message passing. In addition, the receiver should not have to wait if the first send was unsuccessful, also it may at finishing transmitting, the state become inconsistent if stopped transmitting at specific point. At last, it allows obsolete messages/states to be resided in the receiver's message buffer. A protocol was proposed by Holbrook [4], a variation of DIS, allowed the *sender* to decide which messages need to be re-sent at any point in time, and does not allow old messages to be buffered at the receiver where they could become obsolete through using unguaranteed message passing, allowing the *receiver* to decide if a lost message, once it is detected, needs to be resent, it uses "heartbeat" messages to ensure message loss detection, and message log processes to assist in message recovery.

A Stream Control Transmission Protocol (SCTP) [5], is a new protocol similar to TCP as it provides reliable full-duplex connection, in other words, it is a simultaneous two-way data or voice transmission. In addition, it offers new delivery options that suit multimedia applications such as multi-streaming. Also, it allows independent delivery among data streams, multi-homing, allowing end points of a single association to have multiple IP addresses and *partial reliability* and it allows each message to be assigned a delivery reliability level.

G. Drew [6], proposed a network communication protocol for distributed virtual environment which they called an Updatable Queue Abstraction (UQA). The UQA is a simple First in First out (FIFO) queue with the ability of storing additional information, called keyed data, attached with each message. These data give each message special key to represent its type (command, event, of status), and to represent the process that sent the message (process A, process B, etc). The main idea of the UQA is that when node receives the status message, it replaces it with the latest status message of the same sender that stored in its queue. They test the model in one-to-one communication fashion.

The network layer protocol that provides simultaneous unreliable transmission to multiple destination nodes is called multicast protocols. The multicast protocols used whenever the messages need to be sent to multiple nodes. Within DVE, multicast protocols are used extensively as a filtering process.

One of the popular multicast protocol is the overlay multicast. Overlay multicast protocol implemented at the application layer. It is preferred to the Overlay multicast protocol use over the networks that don't offer multicast capability at the network layer. The most known overlay network protocols is the Multicast Backbone(MBone) [7] and the DIVEBone [8] which extended the MBone as a stand-alone part of the DIVE toolkit.

Another multicast protocol called reliable multicast. Reliable multicast protocol refers to error-free eventual delivery of information to all the application with same level of ordering. In reliable

multicast each member of the multicast group is responsible for its own correct reception of all the data using a time-out mechanism.

Sato [9] proposed a reliable multicast protocol suitable for DIAs. The proposed protocol uses the concept of Mutual Aid Regions (MAR). Each MAR has a node that is responsible for acknowledging receipt of packets in that MAR and that sends timeout requests to the nearest MAR if a packet is not received.

Another approach of multicast protocol is the Scalable Communication Protocol for Large-Scale Virtual Environments (SCORE) [10]. SCORE is a scalable multicast-based communication protocol for Large-Scale Virtual Environments (LSVE) work on the Internet. This approach involves the dynamic partitioning of the virtual environment into spatial areas and the association of these areas with multicast groups. It uses a method based on the theory of planar point processes to determine an appropriate cell-size, so that the incoming traffic at the receiver side remains with a given probability below a sufficiently low threshold.

However, multicast protocols have some challenges. First, due to issues such as addressing, many internet routers are limited in the number of groups they can support or they are not multicast aware. Second, it is difficult to implement efficiently on a point to point medium. Finally, it is costly to control and administrate the congestion of the network that results from flooding the network by multicasting. [11]

3. IMPLEMENTATION

We use the QualNet network simulator in our implementation for the distributed virtual environment system. A QualNet is a commercial network simulation tool implemented in C++ that simulates wireless and wired packet mode communication networks. QualNet used in the simulation of MANET, WiMAX networks, satellite networks, wireless sensor networks, etc. It's has a graphical user interface and a sets of library function used for network communication. [13] Our implementation involves three phases. The first phase is generating three types of messages. Since the only message that become obsolete and need to be replaced is the status update message, therefore, we don't need to distinguish between the other two types which are the command and the event message. So, we implemented two types of messages that can be sent by the traffic generator node which are status update message as one type and command or event message as another type of messages.

Phase two involve the implementation of the traffic generator. A traffic generator is the node that generates and sends the message to other nodes in the distributed virtual environment. We use the probability theory to control the traffic generation of the messages. Based on our knowledge, the statues messages represent about two thirds from the total number of messages being sent between two nodes. So we implement the probability of sending the status update message is 70%, while the probability of sending command or event message is 30%. We use the random function to generate the number that used as a probability. The reason in using the random number probability generator, rather than uniform message generator, is to insure the realistic of two task sending information in the real world.

The third phase is implementing the updatable queue abstraction. The updatable queue abstraction algorithm shown in figure 3 and discuss as follow.

When the node receives the message, it first tests if the message is command/event message or not. If so, then it will insert it into the tail of the queue and increase the tail of the queue by one. Else, the message is statues message, then it will retrieve the last message inserted into the queue and check if it command/event message. If so, then the node will insert the retrieved message then the new message into the queue. Else, the node should check if the retrieved message have the same id

number of the new message, in other words, if the message at the end of the queue and new message from the same sender. If the messages from different sender then the node will insert the retrieved message and the new message into the queue, else, if both status messages from the same sender, then the node will remove the retrieved messages and consider it as obsolete message and insert the new statuses message into the queue.

Figure 3: Updatable queue abstraction algorithm.

We apply our implementation on both transport layer communication protocols which are TCP and UDP and called the new modified protocols TCP_UQA and UDP_UQA respectively. Our implementation tested with both one-to-one communication and one-to-many communication as shown in figures 4 and 5 respectively.

Figure 4: one-to-one communication protocol.

Figure 5: one-to-many communication protocol.

4. EXPERIMENTS

To measure the efficiency of VE protocols we perform 96 experiments with the TCP, UDP, TCP-UQA, and UDP-UQA on different packet sizes (32, 256, 512 bytes), where four values (0.0, 0.033, 0.05, 0.1 second) of delay at the receiver were used to represent processes which spend different amounts of time working on other problems than communication.

We have conducted two sets of experiments. The first set was carried to test one-to-one communication between two nodes as in figure 4. Each protocol was tested on the three different packet sizes and on the four different receiver delay values. The source sent 1000 messages to the destination with a 70% probability the message would be a status message and 30% probability to be command and event. Each experiment was run for 180 seconds in which all the 1000 messages were sent by the source.

The second set was carried to test one-to-many communication between one source and four destinations as in figure 5. All of the destination nodes were on the same distance from the source node. Each protocol was tested on the three different packet sizes and on the four different receiver delay values. The source sent 1000 messages for each destination with a 70% probability the message would be a status message and 30% probability to be command and event. Each experiment was run for 720 seconds in which all the 4000 messages were sent by the source.

5. RESULTS

To study the efficiency of the tested protocols we measured the average value of all experiments carried on the three different packet sizes (32, 256, 512 bytes). Figures 6 to 10 show the one-to-one communication results and Figures 11 to 13 show the one-to-many communication results.

For one-to-one communication, Figure 6 presented the results of average client throughput. The UDP and UDP-UQA protocols showed the best results for all packet sizes at the all receiver delays, because the client would only require transmitting the requested messages without any additional packets. While TCP protocol spent additional time in transmitting acknowledgements for each packet it sends. TCP-UQA showed the worst results for all cases, because in addition to the time spent in transmitting acknowledgements it spent additional time in updating the queue.

Figure 7 presented the average server throughput. TCP protocol was the worst because of sending acknowledgements, so the server is forced to process the acknowledgements in addition to the messages. While TCP-UQA protocol showed better results, because of sending less messages and thus fewer acknowledgements. Both UDP and UDP-UQA protocols were the best, Both nearly showed the same results in all test cases, except that UDP-UQA protocol was not efficient when sending packets of size 256 bytes. Unless of this impact the average server throughput of UDP-UQA still better than TCP and TCP-UQA protocols.

From figures 8, 9, 10, a closer look can be carried on the queue management of each protocol. UDP had the longest average queue and the highest difference from the average peak queue size, which meant that the queue size was not stable and all messages arrived at once to the queue which in turn increased the average time of the message in the queue. While UDP-UQA protocol showed better results only because of dealing with fewer number of messages but still suffer from unstable queue size and low queue service rate. Surprisingly, Both TCP and TCP-UQA protocols showed shorter average queue lengths and smaller peaks than both UDP and UDP-UQA protocols because of staggering [12]. TCP-UQA was the most stable queue and the highest queue service rate.

Figure 6: One-To-One average client throughput (bit/s).

Figure 7: One-To-One average server throughput (bit/s).

Figure 8: One-To-One average queue length.

Figure 9: One-To-One average peak queue size.

Figure 10: One-To-One average time in the queue.

For one-to-many communication, figure 11 presented the results of average queue length. The best protocol was TCP-UQA for all test cases. While UDP protocol was the worst at the receiver delay value of 0.033, 0.05, and 0.1 second. UDP-UQA protocol showed results better than both UDP and TCP protocols. From figures 12 and 13 we could see that UDP-UQA showed more stability than one-to-one communication but still suffer from slow queue service rate because of congestion of messages in the queue. UDP-UQA protocol showed better results than UDP protocol in all test cases.

Figure 11: One-To-Many average queue length.

Figure 12: One-To-Many average peak queue size.

Figure 13: One-To-Many average time in the queue.

6. CONCLUSION

Distributed virtual environments raise new issues to the communication protocols upon the variety of tasks and variety of messages. Several protocols were proposed to improve and meet DVE communication requirements.

In this paper we have implemented UQA on both the original TCP and UDP protocols. Surprisingly, TCP-UQA showed better queue management than other protocols for both small and large messages. This advantage of TCP-UQA makes it a good candidate when each object state is important and cannot be neglected or missed such considering virtual medicine environments, while UDP-UQA did not show a tangible difference in its performance when compared with UDP. TCP-UQA was slower than other protocols in some cases because of its additional processing on each message; this disadvantage makes it a bad candidate for time-restricted application.

All test cases were run on uni-cast protocols. UQA have many advantages can benefit from by implementing it on multicast protocols. We will consider this for future work.

7. REFERENCES

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